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Review of *Lion of The Desert*

Lion of The Desert is a historical war film produced in 1981 by filmmaker Moustapha Akkad which covers the events of the Italian colonization of Libya and subsequent Libyan resistance under the Senussi-Sufi general Umar al-Mukhtar (nicknamed the “Lion of the Desert”). The film is a historical war film and, in its beginning, claims to be a historically accurate representation of the second Italo-Senussi conflict, claiming to represent both “real characters and historical events”. The content of this review will largely cover the events of the film itself, and key details of the movie in comparison to the actual events of the Libyan resistance and Italian colonization in the early 20th century, and the film’s accuracies and inaccuracies in portraying these events and cultures correctly.

Lion of The Desert begins by portraying fascist Italy in the early 20th century under dictator Benito Mussolini. This was during the period of Italian colonization of Libya, from 1911 to 1943, where hundreds of thousands of Italians, with military support, forcibly seized and settled Bedouin land in Northern Libya [1]. The film depicts fascist leader Mussolini ordering that Umar al Mukhtar, a powerful Libyan warrior and resistance fighter, be captured dead or alive and prosecuted for rebelling against the Italian colonization of Libya. Umar al Mukhtar was originally a Quran teacher and is introduced in the film teaching students the holy scripture

[16]. He is shown as notorious amongst the Italian military as a brave yet elusive rebel leader who repeatedly embarrasses the Italian military during battle and manages to inflict heavy casualties upon the technologically superior Italian forces. Despite his ferocity and courage in battle, Mukhtar's mercy and piety is shown after a major ambush when he stops his fighters from killing captured Italian forces. When one of his students remarks "they do it to us", Mukhtar replies "they are not our teachers". In response to these ambushes, the Italian military becomes increasingly vicious and draconian against the Bedouin people as a form of collective punishment for Mukhtar's armed resistance. They enter villages and massacre the inhabitants, plunder the wealth of the villages, and set fire to the structures. Anyone accused of collaborating with Mukhtar is executed, and thousands of other Bedouin civilians are captured and sent to concentration camps. Mukhtar continues his military resistance against the Italian military for almost 20 years. Eventually, Mukhtar was captured by Italian forces, and before being put on trial, knowing his immense influence and popularity, he was offered lavish bribes in order to give up his armed struggle. Mukhtar refuses these bribes as he does not feel comfortable living a life of luxury while his people are in concentration camps. The film ends with Mukhtar being charged with high treason by the Italian government, and publicly executed by hanging in front of a large crowd of Bedouins.

The film has both strengths and weaknesses when it comes to historical and cultural accuracy. Many of the events in the film are historically accurate, and many of the battles and ambushes depicted are reported to have occurred during the Italian occupation of Libya. As depicted in the film, Umar al Mukhtar actually was a Quran teacher before he became a

resistance fighter [3], and the ambush where he spared the life of Italian prisoners also is reported to have actually occurred historically [2]. Perhaps these accuracies are due to the support of the Libyan government under President Gaddafi, which financially sponsored the creation of *Lion of The Desert* [10], and motivated the filmmakers to try to be as historically accurate as reasonably possible given the time and resource constraints of a three-hour film with limited actors.

Despite its strengths, the film also has several weaknesses when it comes to historical and cultural accuracy. The most major cultural flaw in the portrayal of Umar al-Mukhtar in the film *Lion of The Desert* is a lack of reference to his Sufi background and upbringing. It is well-known that Mukhtar was a member of the North African Sanusiyyah Sufi order (or tariqa), which was popular in modern-day Libya, Algeria, and Egypt during the 19th and early 20th centuries [2][3]. The order was founded by Sīdī Muḥammad ibn ‘Alī al-Sanūsī al-Mujāhirī al-Ḥasanī al-Idrīsī in 1837 [13] and quickly gained extensive popularity in the Cyrenaica region of Eastern Libya [3][4][7]. The Sanusi order, like many other North African Sufi orders, is known for its distinguishing practices and theology which includes distinct *dhikr* (verbal remembrance of God), *wird* (recitation of Qur’an or other scriptures and prayers), repeated *majalis* (spiritual gatherings), and even the concept of *bay’ah* (allegiance to a spiritual guide by a seeker) [5][6]. The order is also known for its founder’s stance against *taqlid* (blind-following of a school of Islamic law) and encouragement of *ijtihad* (self-interpretation of religious texts) [6][14]. Despite the cultural richness of the Sanusi Tariqah, the film makes zero reference to it or any of its distinct practices or influence in the region. The film does not even depict a single *zawiyat* or

Sufi religious lodge, which were used extensively by the Sanusiyyah in the early 20th century [14], for both religious, economic, and military purposes [3][7]. It fails to mention that Umar al-Mukhtar himself was an ardent member of the Senusi order, along with many of his fighters and supporters [3].

Other minor flaws in the film include historical inaccuracies, such as Mukhtar having no last words in the film, whereas in reality he was reported to have recited the last 3 verses of *Surat al-Fajr* in the Qur'an as his final words: "O soul that is at rest! Return to your Lord, well-pleased (with Him), well-pleasing (to Him). So join My servants, and enter My Paradise" (Quran 89:27-30) [3][8]. The film also seems to oversimplify Mukhtar's almost 20 year-long campaign of resistance against the Italian forces, only showing a select few battles and featuring a few dozen fighters in the film compared to the actual forces of Mukhtar which were estimated to be between one and three thousand men who fought almost 250 battles per year [2][3]. This oversimplification of the actual forces needed for battle is expected, though, as the filmmakers only had a couple of hours and only so many actors to portray Mukhtar's campaigns.

The producer of this film, Moustapha Akkad, was originally from Aleppo in Northern Syria [9][11]. He was Muslim himself and sought to bring wider awareness in the Western world towards Islam. Speaking about another film he produced about the prophet Muhammad, Akkad stated his justification for making films about Islam and Muslim figures: "I did the films because it is a personal thing for me ... Being a Muslim myself who lived in the west I felt that it was my obligation my duty to tell the truth about Islam. It is a religion that has a 700 million following, yet it's so little known about which surprised me. I thought I should tell the story that will bring

this [history] to the west” [11]. Akkad, as a Syrian and Muslim himself, was clearly sympathetic towards Muslim causes, and sought to portray Muslim resistance to Italian colonization in this film as heroic, justified, and praiseworthy. This contrasts with the Italian government’s perspective on the film, which led them to ban *Lion of The Desert* in 1982 for being “damaging” to the honor of the country’s military [12]. Akkad knew his audience would be largely non-Muslim, and he sought to present a positive image of Islam and Muslims as liberators fighting against colonialism, with justice, faith and integrity [15]. Akkad is able to portray Mukhtar and his forces as brave and heroically anti-colonial, which draws sympathy from Western viewers towards Muslim liberation struggles by connecting them with anti-colonial struggle (and oppressor-vs-oppressed dynamics) [15]. Western viewers during the period the film was released are likely to sympathize with Omar al-Mukhtar and other Muslim freedom fighters, at a time when imperialism was declining and large empires giving freedom to their former colonies in the late 20th century. Akkad intentionally released this film about a lesser-known Muslim anti-colonial struggle in Libya in order to portray Muslims in a more positive light, as freedom-fighters fighting colonial oppression worldwide, similar to other formerly colonized freedom-seeking groups in this time period. Akkad’s consideration of his audience likely influenced him to make movies featuring Muslims portraying heroic roles, such as Umar al-Mukhtar in *Lion of The Desert*, and also *The Message*, which was about the life and battles of the Prophet Muhammad.

In conclusion, the film *Lion of The Desert* has both strengths and weaknesses in covering the cultural and historical nuances of the Libyan resistance to Italian colonization under Omar

al-Mukhtar. It does a decent job of covering historical events and battles with a limited amount of time and resources, despite having a few minor historical inaccuracies. However, when it comes to the cultural background of Omar al-Mukhtar and Libya as a whole, the film does not make adequate mention of the importance of Sufism in this anti-colonial struggle. Although Akkad was from a Muslim background, which allowed him to cover this lesser-known anti-colonial struggle in a positive light, he neglects to highlight the Sufi influence and background in the story of Omar al-Mukhtar. This is the most major flaw of the film, and a significant one because a large part of the cultural and societal structure in 20th century Libya was due to the hierarchical societal structure of the Sufi orders [5][14]. The only major changes to this film that should be made are an inclusion of Sufi ideology and practices amongst Mukhtar and his people in order to show how they were able to empower the Libyan anti-colonial struggle, and a wider emphasis on Sufism as the bedrock of North African society in this time period in order to be culturally and historically accurate, along with other minor changes such as adding Mukhtar's real final words to the film.

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